

Technical Report on Land Use Policy Coherence Analysis for the Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)

Please cite as: K Blackstock, H Nicholson, A Juarez-Bourke, G Martinez Sanchez, S Poskitt, K Matthews, J Boucher, J Glendinning, A Green, S Martinat, I Merrell & S Thomson. (2024) Technical Report on Land Use Policy Coherence for the Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1), Project Deliverable D5.3, 47 pages.

The James Hutton Institute is supported by the Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS). Research funded through grant JHI-C3-1; SRUC-C3-1, BioSS-UNC-7 Provision of biomathematical & statistical services and previous Strategic Research Programmes.

Contents

1	Summary	4
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Why is policy coherence analysis important?	6
2.2	Focus of the policy coherence analysis	6
3	Methodology.....	7
3.1	Broad coherence screening.....	7
3.2	In-depth policy coherence	9
3.3	Visualisation of coherence relationships	10
4	Findings	11
4.1	Horizontal Coherence.....	11
4.1.1	Working towards common outcomes	11
4.1.2	How are policies connected to each other?	12
4.2	In-depth Coherence for the sub-set of agricultural policies	15
4.2.1	Recent changes in Scottish Agricultural Policy	15
4.2.2	Vertical Coherence of Agricultural Policy	16
4.2.3	Coherence Relationships	18
4.3	Coherence within Government.....	21
4.3.1	Policy Owners.....	22
4.3.2	Policy enforcers.....	23
5	Summary answers to our research questions:	25
5.1	Are there synergies, gaps or conflicts in the way current land use policies are supporting land use transformations?	25
5.2	Are there problems of vertical, diagonal and/or horizontal coherence within existing land use policies?.....	26
5.3	How could policy coherence support land use transformations?	27
5.4	What are the opportunities to improve or sustain coherence?	28
5.5	How can coherence be monitored more effectively in the future?	29
6	Policy Implications	30
7	Next Steps	30
	Annex 1: List of Policy Documents used in Horizontal Screening.....	32
	Annex 2: List of Goals used for horizontal coherence screening.....	34
	Annex 3: Policy Abbreviations	35
	Annex 4: Table of policy relationships	38

Annex 5: Table of policy owners43
References:46

1 Summary

This briefing is a deliverable from the [Land Use Transformations](#) project (JHI-C3-1) within the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27. It focusses on the Policy Coherence Analysis within the work package *Joined up approaches to managing land* (WP3.2).

Policy coherence is important to help deliver aspirations for transformations in how Scottish land is managed to deliver a suite of objectives, exemplified in the objectives of the Agriculture and Rural Communities (2023) Bill.

Policy coherence means connecting the objectives, instruments and implementation practices within a policy; and between different policies, including across different policy domains.

The main findings are:

- There are many references between policies which cover the gamut of land use topics, suggesting a strong foundation for coherence.
- However, there is less evidence of the policies contributing to a transformation through systemically considering a range of land use goals.
- There are few reciprocal relationships, suggesting it is important to check that policy coherence expectations are understood, agreed and acted upon when the links is one-way.
- Vertical coherence is practiced within the agricultural policy documents we reviewed, but the relationships are often implied and hard to trace.
- Non-agricultural policies sometimes depend on agricultural instruments (e.g. cross-compliance, or incentives within the SRDP) to deliver their objectives.
- There are policies with shared 'ownership' or 'enforcement' relationships between different policy directorates, generating the pre-conditions for coherence.
- There is though little evidence of how coherence is, or will be, delivered, but the ambitions and breadth of policies is increasing.
- Attention to gaps, acknowledging conflicts or trade-offs, and monitoring how coherence creates substantive changes 'on the ground' are opportunities to improve coherence in policy design and implementation.

The main findings are also summarised in a [briefing](#) and an [infographic](#).

2 Introduction

This technical report is an output from the project (JHI-C3-1) within the Scottish Government’s Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27. It focusses on the Policy Coherence Analysis within the work package *Joined up approaches to managing land* (WP3.2). The methodological design has been and continues to be developed, iteratively since April 2022. Initial data collection, analysis and interpretation were undertaken from November 2022 to September 2023 and recorded in a Milestone Report (M24). Further analysis was subsequently conducted September 2023 to February 2024 to generate this deliverable.

The purpose of the document, as project Deliverable D5, is to report on results of the policy coherence analysis, suggest implications for policy, and outline next steps for 2024 – 2025.

The purpose of the governance work in WP3.2 is to respond to one of the overall Land Use Transformation project research questions (RQ2) to explore whether **by joining up approaches to managing land it is possible to make more effective use of land in delivering the range of public and private goods**. The governance analysis is focussed on understanding the institutional levers for joined up policies that govern land use for climate, environment, and socio-economic outcomes.

Policy coherence assesses the extent to which multiple separate policies, working towards the same or similar overall objectives, are consistent, or whether they in fact generate unintended conflicts or contradictions [1]. We can usefully distinguish between two types of policy coherence: horizontal coherence (between different policies) and vertical coherence (within policies, across their objectives, instruments and implementation)[2]. A further policy coherence type emerged during the initial analysis, which is diagonal coherence (whereby the objectives of one policy are achieved through the instruments or implementation of another policy). These three types of coherence are the focus of this report and can be seen diagrammatically in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Policy Coherence Framework (adapted from Blackstock et al. 2018)[3]

2.1 Why is policy coherence analysis important?

The Scottish Government is currently facilitating potentially the most radical change to agriculture in many decades, through its ongoing Agricultural Reform Programme. This is taking place during other, wider, changes in the land use policy landscape (c.f. [Agricultural Reform Route Map \(ruralpayments.org\)](https://www.ruralpayments.org/)). Scotland is not alone in reforming its agriculture practices considering current crises [4, 5]. There is growing acknowledgement that responding to the climate, biodiversity and socio-economic crises requires radical change, but that any transformation requires a 'just transition'. This is necessary first to ensure that the transformation is seen as necessary and legitimate to secure the cooperation of land managers. Secondly so that rural land use continues to provide an appropriate balance of multiple benefits for people while staying within planetary boundaries, protecting and where possible restoring nature [2, 6-9]. Meeting the challenge of these myriad, interconnected, and complex crises necessitates that multiple policies are enacted on rural land, often in relation to different land uses and activities, and with subtly different priorities, or even conflicting, goals and principles in mind (e.g. farming, forestry, recreation and sport, conservation, climate change mitigation and adaptation, livelihoods and wellbeing, etc)[10]. It is therefore essential to analyse if and how these multiple policies relate to each other[6, 11]. Are these policies complementary? Do they undermine each other? Are there trade-offs and how does the balance between objectives get articulated and deliberated on, and decided? How can policies combine to facilitate the required transformations and be perceived as effective and legitimate by those who live, work or visit rural areas? 'Policy coherence' is an approach that helps to assess and analyse these questions.

2.2 Focus of the policy coherence analysis

The policy coherence analysis focussed on Scottish, national-level, government policies affecting land use and land use change. As with the rest of the project, land use was defined broadly to include a range of land-based business sectors[12]. These include 'traditional' agriculture and forestry land uses, but also other land uses such as recreation, housing and renewable energy.

The approach is concerned with the actors involved in land use and land use change decisions, as befits the governance framing of the topic, so the analysis is less concerned with land cover change or the monitoring of biophysical changes in environmental conditions.

The research questions guiding this research are detailed below with those in bold being where the data analysis has focussed to date:

- **Are there synergies, gaps or conflicts in the way current land use policies are supporting land use transformations?**
- **Are there problems of vertical, diagonal and/or horizontal coherence within existing land use policies?**
- How could policy coherence support land use transformations?

- What are the opportunities to improve or sustain coherence?
- How can coherence be monitored more effectively in the future?

3 Methodology

The initial design of the methodology, research questions, and work plan, developed between SRUC and Hutton researchers, is captured in milestone M7 [13]. The methodology consisted of desk-based policy analysis, interviews and meetings with analysts, officials and policy advisors. It was developed and implemented in the context of a dynamic policy landscape, with more information appearing around changes to the 'land use' policy context such as the Agricultural Reform Routemap (February/June 2023), the Land Use and Agriculture Just Transitions Plan (June 2023), and the Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill (September 2023). There was also a change of political leadership for the governing party, although the administration's structure did not change. The methodology therefore developed iteratively, adapting over time, and remained responsive to changes both in the policy environment, and insights from our data, as we progressed.

The approach considered horizontal (connection between policies) and vertical (connection within policies) coherence across three levels – objectives, instruments/measures and implementation, further analysing diagonal connections as they emerged.

3.1 Broad coherence screening

This exercise was designed as a rapid review of the policies to assess the extent to which they aligned with goals associated with land use transformation, specifically (1) climate mitigation, (2) biodiversity, (3) climate adaptation, (4) rural prosperity, and (5) justice and inclusion (see Annex 2). These five goals were determined by the research team, based on the Programme for Government 2022, the existing National Performance Framework, *Delivering our vision for Scottish Agriculture 2022* and *Sustainable and regenerative agriculture statement 2022*. The definition of 'transformation' followed the entry in the Land Use Transformation project Glossary [14].

Initial searches generated a long list of 134 policies related to land use and land use change in rural Scotland. These were reduced to 60 policies through a prioritisation process by the research team. The short list was checked during interviews, and an additional four policies were added based on interviewee feedback. Additionally, in the latter half of 2023, the Scottish Government introduced a new Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill. The Bill is designed to make provisions for the support of agriculture and rural communities, and effectively assumes the role of European Union (EU) Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) legislation, transposed into UK and Scottish law, following the UK's exit from the EU. Considering the significance of this Bill for policies associated with land use transformations, moving forward, the research team agreed it was important to add this to the analysis. Similarly, the Scottish Government published an updated version of the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy (Scottish Biodiversity Strategy to 2045 – Tackling the nature emergency (2023)). Considering that an earlier consultation in relation to this steering strategy had already been included in the analysis, we decided that the updated, published version should also be

included. Therefore, a total of 66 policies was included in the analysis. These policies are listed in Annex 1: List of Policy Documents used in Horizontal Screening.

As shown in Tables 1 and 2, below, the sampled policies come from a range of policy domains and mechanisms. However, a potential weakness of the sample may be a scarcity of Skills and Food and Drink policies, which were highlighted in our interviews as important to the overall quest for Land Use Transformations.

Table 1: Policy domains of policies analysed

Policy domains	Count
Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries (AFF)	23
Environment	21
Climate Change	5
Socio-Economic	17

Table 2: Types of policy

Policy mechanism	Count
Primary legislation	18
Steering Strategy	36
Instrument	12

To analyse the horizontal coherence of these policies, an MS-Excel spreadsheet template was set up with each policy document having its own row, and a series of analytical criteria across the columns. Metadata included the name, date and weblink to the document(s) read for the row. The analytical criteria were as follows:

The Goals Spreadsheet for broad coherence screening

- Objectives of each policy.
- Type of policy mechanism.
- Topic and domain areas covered by the policy and the relationships between them.
- Appraisal of how well the policy addresses each of the goals and whether the policy was judged to be transformational.

To analyse the vertical and diagonal coherence of the policies, a second spreadsheet was created, similarly with each policy document allocated to each row, and a series of analytical criteria in the columns. These criteria can be summarised as concentrating on the following themes:

The Policy Coherence Spreadsheet for in-depth coherence analysis

- Objectives of each policy.
- Type of policy mechanism.
- Topic and domain areas covered by the policy and the relationships between them.
- Responsibilities in relation to the policy (i.e. ownership and enforcement).
- Budget associated with the policy (if any).
- Instruments and implementation of the policy.
- Coherence relationships with other policies.

Each policy document was read in detail by a team member, who subsequently populated the cells for the analytical criteria, for each policy. Claims made in the policy documents were taken at 'face value', rather than checking to see if the narrative claims were met by evidence of change and positive impacts. Data were entered for each cell across a row (i.e., for the single policy document) in both the goals and coherence spreadsheets. Options included closed categories and free form notes.

For the analysis of horizontal coherence, individual team members were also allocated one of the goals and its associated analytical criteria to analyse the data and write up a research memo. This ensured that there was a crosscheck between data entered for each policy and the patterns found under each goal and analytical criteria. Any inconsistencies in interpretation or factual errors were discussed in team meetings and rectified if needed.

The draft findings and our interpretations from this analysis were then peer reviewed by policy makers within Scottish Government through interviews with six individuals working within Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate, during February and March 2023.

3.2 In-depth policy coherence

Due to the fast-paced policy environment we sought to enhance the relevance of our coherence analysis by focusing on and further interrogating a subset of 11 policies associated with the current agriculture support programme and information on how these policies might be reformed. These were:

- [Scottish Rural Development Programme](#) (SRDP)
- [Agriculture \(Retained EU Law and Data\) \(Scotland\) Act 2020](#)
- [The Common Agricultural Policy \(Cross-Compliance\) \(Scotland\) Regulations 2014](#)
- [Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions](#) (GAECs)
- [Less Favoured Area Support Scheme](#) (LFASS)
- [Agri-Environment Climate Scheme \(AECS\) 2022](#)
- [Delivering our vision for Scottish Agriculture 2022: Proposals for a new Agriculture Bill](#)
- [Sustainable and regenerative agriculture statement 2022](#) (also known as the Vision Statement)
- [Agricultural Reform Route map 2023](#)
- [Land Use and Agriculture Just Transition Plan Discussion Paper 2023](#).
- [Agriculture and Rural Communities \(Scotland\) Bill 2023](#)

Note that the Scottish Rural Development Plan (SRDP), Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS), Agri-Environment Climate Measures (AECS), Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs), and Cross compliance were included as separate rows, as there were three different documents analysed.

The data for these 11 policies from the MS-Excel spreadsheets and interviews were then considered in more depth, including going back to the original policy documents to check specific aspects. Research summary memos were written for each document, considering the vertical, diagonal, and horizontal coherence relationships, and coherence diagrams created for the current and proposed policy arrangements. These draft findings were shared

with invited colleagues from RESAS and Scottish Government Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate in June 2023 for feedback.

3.3 Visualisation of coherence relationships

Having completed the initial policy coherence analysis, we explored ways to visualise the findings and present them in a way that enabled holistic observations of coherence across the entire sample [15]. We used R 4.3.3 to visualise the connections between the policies in our sample. Through the creation of a spreadsheet that included the data on policy domain, type, and connections, we were able to use R to illustrate all these aspects within the diagrams (Figure 3 and Figure 5) presented in the Findings section next. We used these visualisations not only to present the data but also as part of our analysis, as it helped us identify patterns and links between the policies, as well as issues with the data that needed to be further investigated.

To better visualize our results, we abbreviated the policy names. The table of abbreviations can be seen in Annex 3: Policy Abbreviations.

4 Findings

The findings are presented in four parts:

1. Findings from analysis of horizontal coherence (section 4.1);
2. Findings from analysis of in-depth coherence (section 4.2); and
3. Findings related to references between government directorates (section 4.3).

4.1 Horizontal Coherence

The horizontal coherence relationships were assessed firstly through the broad coherence screening and then using the visualisations. This section covers results from both analyses.

4.1.1 Working towards common outcomes

The initial horizontal coherence analysis focussed on whether the policies were working towards common goals¹ (i.e., horizontal coherence of objectives). Initial analysis (shown in Figure 2) suggested that most policies were addressing climate mitigation (Goal 1), biodiversity restoration (Goal 2) and economic prosperity (Goal 4), but there were fewer policies addressing climate adaptation (Goal 3) or inclusion/social justice (Goal 5). Surprisingly, climate change policies did not mention much on adaptation, suggesting the dominance of net zero (mitigation) approaches over adaptation responses. Conversely, policies regarding ‘socio-economic’ issues tended to be less likely to address biodiversity objectives; and even these categories of policies, focussed on energy, planning, tourism etc, did not always address issues of prosperity or social justice. Although the age of a document had some bearing, with climate and justice concerns becoming more apparent in later documents, this was not always the case.

Figure 2: Breakdown of which types of policies address each goal (goals described in Annex 2) The percentages show the percentage of policies within that policy domain addressing each goal.

Furthermore, there were differences in whether goals were addressed depending on the focal domain of the policy, as shown in Figure 2. The ‘traditional’ land use policies were

¹ Please see Annex 2: List of Goals used for horizontal coherence screening for definitions. AFF refers to policies for agriculture and forestry; CC for climate change policies; Env for biodiversity and environment policies; and socio-economic for other land related policies (e.g. energy, planning, tourism). The List of policies can be found in Annex 1: List of Policy Documents used in Horizontal Screening.

assessed, based on the claims within the official policy documents, as supporting many goals; whereas the socio-economic policies (energy, recreation, planning) did not cover as many goals, in particular, there were few of these policies addressing inclusion and justice for example.

The 66 policies were also screened to see if they were contributing towards transformation. Here, only a few (18%) of the policies addressed all five goals. In total, we judged half the sample as trying to advance transformation. No policy was judged as retarding transformation, but half the sample were neutral, including some recent policy documents. The documents with more transformational ambitions tended to be steering strategies with limited, if any, targets, indicators or dedicated funding available to them.

One reflection on the analysis of horizontal coherence between policy objectives was the lack of any explicit recognition of actual or potential conflict between objectives as stated in the policy documents. As presented, where multiple policy goals were being sought, the information in the documents suggested that these multiple goals do not conflict, could be synergistic and can be achieved with the instruments available. However, potential conflicts between policy objectives were asked about in the interviews, and here some references were made to tensions between food production and environmental goals.

The broad screening coherence analysis did not have the capacity to address the relationships between 66 policy documents across **all three levels** (objectives, instruments, implementation). Rather the focus was on whether there were shared **objectives** pulling towards the same 'vision' for transformation in the land use sector. This focus on only one part of coherence was selected to provide early feedback on the degree of ambition required for the policies being developed across the Land Use and Agriculture Change Plan, particularly the proposed reforms of agricultural support programme.

4.1.2 How are policies connected to each other?

The analysis of horizontal coherence also included an examination, conducted using R, of connectivity between 54 of the policies², including connections across policy domains. The results of this analysis are visualised in Figure 3, below. As the figure shows, the analysis revealed a plethora of connections between different policies (169 connections in total). To some extent this is encouraging, as it shows awareness of the importance of policies working together to achieve goals of transformation and an appetite for working across different silos. As shown in *Table 3* below, it is mainly steering strategies that are making the connections between policies and across different policy domains – the only primary legislation that is linking to policies in different domains is the proposed Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill (2023).

² The diagram in Figure 33 does not include any policy instruments, to make the diagram easier to read than with all 66 policies in our sample. We believe, for this visualisation of the broad screening, the key relationships are visible through the inclusion of the steering strategies and primary legislation. The instruments are included in Figure 6, where we visualise our in-depth analysis.

Figure 3: Coherence between the different policy domains. The squares represent primary legislation and circles represent steering strategies. The sample shown is 54 as it excludes policy instruments. Gold refers to Agriculture, Fishery and Forestry policies; Pink to Socio-Economic policies; Green to Environmental policies; and Blue to Climate policies. The policies in the bold border are further analysed in Figure 5. Coloured arrows show references between the referencing policies and the policies that are referenced. Red arrows show reciprocal relationships. See Annex 3: Policy Abbreviations and Annex 4: Table of policy relationships for more information.

There were six entities, shown without connections in the diagram, that do not make an explicit reference to any of the policies in our sample, though they do reference other policies we did not research. Four of the six policies where this occurred were from 2010 or earlier, and so their age may be the reason for their lack of reference to other policies in our sample. However, two (Tourism in Scotland (2018) and Management of wild deer (2020))

were from 2018 or later so it is surprising for these to lack connections to our sample policies.

Table 3: Main nodes for Coherence. An extended table of the information produced from Figure 3 can be found in Annex 4.

Abbreviated Policy Name	How many other policies does it link to?	Links to AFF Land Use	Links to Socio-Economic Land Use	Links to Environment	Links to Climate Change
Just transition (LU) 2023	13	5	2	2	4
Agriculture bill 2023	17	11	0	3	3
Ag routemap 2023	8	6	0	1	1
CCAP 2019	8	3	2	3	0
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	9	2	2	3	2
Environment strategy 2020	8	0	3	3	2
NPF4 2021	9	3	4	2	0
Econ trans strategy 2022	8	0	4	2	2
Islands plan 2019	10	1	4	2	3
Bute house 2021	9	2	5	1	1

Eagle-eyed readers may find some examples in Figure 3 where policies appear to reference policies that were not yet published. In some cases, e.g. Crofting natural development plan 2021 referring to the Biodiversity Strategy 2023, the document shows that this policy was anticipated, and references were made to the forthcoming strategy. In other cases, e.g. Biomass Action Plan (2007) referencing SRDP 2021, the plan references SRDP 2007-2013. However, to include multiple versions of the SRDP available in the past 20 years would be visually distracting. We also assumed that unless otherwise clearly indicated the linkage would continue to be valid and carried forward to the latest SRDP programme.

There were also very few ($n=6$) policies that made references to other policies in all four policy domains; there were three AFF policies (Just Transition LU (2023), Vision for Agriculture (2022), Crofting plan (2021)); one Environment policy (Biodiversity Strategy, 2023); and two socio-economic policies (Islands Plan, 2019 and Bute House, 2021). Note that there were no climate change policies in our sample that covered all four domains. There were relatively fewer connections visible in the bottom half of the Figure 3, suggesting that environmental and socio-economic policies associated with land use do not have as many stated connections.

Only 13 of the 169 connections were reciprocal (i.e. two policies referring to each other, as opposed to just one referring to another), which are indicated by the red connectors in Figure 3 and reproduced in Table 4. Of these 13, four involve references to policies in different policy domains and in all four cases, these references are between environment and socio-economic policy domains. In part, the small number of reciprocal policies can be

explained by the timing of different policies, in that policies generally do not refer to future policies (unless imminently expected). Nonetheless, the limited number of visible reciprocal relationships indicates that there are few policies that cross reference each other. Given the fact that most coherence relationships are necessarily ‘one-way’ it is therefore important that policies are aware of what is being expected of them in terms of having mutually coherent objectives. Different policies may thus be unaware of implied connections made to them by others, particularly where policies are crossing between different policy domains.

Table 4: 13 reciprocal references in our sample

Policy A	Policy B
Agri and rural communities bill 2023	Agri reform route map 2023
Agri and rural communities bill 2023	Agriculture act 2020
Climate change (emissions) act 2019	Climate change act 2009
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	Environment strategy 2020
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	NPF4 2021
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	River basin management plan 2021
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	Strategy for economic transformation 2022
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	NPF4 2021
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	River basin management plan 2021
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	Strategy for economic transformation 2022
Energy strategy 2017	Strategy for economic transformation 2022
NPF4 2021	Strategy for economic transformation 2022

4.2 In-depth Coherence for the sub-set of agricultural policies

This section covers the in-depth analysis of a subset of 11 agricultural policies, shown in bold in Figure 3. The analysis covers three aspects – the changes over time of the main agricultural policies; the way the current agricultural policies were vertically coherent at the time of analysis; and the various coherence relationships observed for the 11 policies. This focus was selected to support the proposed future (post 2025) agricultural reform programme.

4.2.1 Recent changes in Scottish Agricultural Policy

One of the first findings was the need to understand change over time, showing the move from the EU compliant agriculture support policies, through the policies under the 2020 Act that managed the EU withdrawal process, to the current reform to generate new agricultural policy. It is possible to interpret the Agricultural Reform Routemap as signalling a step change in Scotland’s agricultural policy, which had previously been constrained in its evolution over time by the need to conform with the parent European Union’s Common Agricultural Policy.

As Figure 4 shows, there were a number of simultaneous or overlapping consultation and vision documents (see the light gold items in Figure 4) being developed and deployed in the transition phase from the current agricultural policy framework to the proposed future agricultural support scheme. These were also challenging to fit within a coherence framework due to their provisional nature. However, we did include some of these, as the

documents provided strong narrative signals on the need to increase the pace and ambition of change, to broaden the objectives of agricultural policy to include climate and conservation actions and issues of justice and inclusion. The 11 policies discussed in section 4.2.3 are highlighted in bold.

Figure 4: Recent changes in Scottish agricultural policy. The agriculture related policies selected for in depth analysis relating to the Agricultural Reform Programme are highlighted in bold and with a black outline. Lighter gold refers to Scottish Government documents stating the process of developing new agricultural policy and inviting feedback from stakeholders.

Looking to the new Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill (2023) and the wider agricultural support reform programme, the work for horizontal and diagonal coherence looks set to increase. The references from the Bill increase to 17 links from the Bill to others, compared to just one link from the Agricultural Act (2020). So, in addition to the strategies, plans and instruments already connected horizontally, vertically or diagonally (see section 4.2.3), there are further policies to align agricultural policy with, including the Good Food Nation Act (2022); Environment Strategy (2020); proposed Natural Environment Bill (2024); Biodiversity Strategy (2023); Cleaner Air for Scotland Strategy (2015); Flood Resilience Strategy (2023) and the new Land Reform Bill (2024). These policies introduce new plans that will require coherence between objectives, instruments and in their implementation. The mechanisms for delivering these broader ambitions in these vision documents were somewhat clarified by the publication of the new Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill (2023). However, whilst this primary legislation provides the ability for detailed secondary legislation to be developed, the exact content and interactions of the Tiers within the proposed reform programme remain unclear.

4.2.2 Vertical Coherence of Agricultural Policy

Our analysis shows the way that Scottish agricultural policy must comply with UK and global policies, but not with EU policy anymore, since the UK withdrawal from the European Union.

We found there was a raft of documents with different (sub)objectives (shown in Figure 5) sitting below the primary legislation Agricultural (Retained EU Law and Data) (Scotland) (2020). This Act had objectives relating the procedural aspects associated with the EU withdrawal, rather than providing a coherent objective that provides a framework for the instruments’ objectives as shown in Figure 5. However, the Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill, supporting the developing agricultural reform programme has ambitious and wide-ranging objectives that we expect will provide the framing for the proposed tiers (see Figure 5 below).

Figure 5: Current vertical coherence within Scottish Agricultural Policy³. The figure shows that Scottish agricultural policy must cohere with supra-Scottish processes (at the top); that there are a range of policy objectives related to different instruments (third row down); and these instruments are implemented by a range of policy actors in different institutions (fifth row down). The boxes at the bottom relate to different forms of monitoring and evaluation in use to provide feedback loops to the Scottish and supra-national primary legislation.

We found that the degree of vertical policy coherence was difficult to assess, as the policy documents did not always explicitly cross-reference one another, or their parent policies under which they were nested. This makes the relationships between them quite opaque to non-experts on agricultural policy. This lack of explicit linkage matters if one is seeking effective coherence between the many land-related policies being developed (as shown in the Land and Agriculture Change Plan). The different policy initiators, advisers, designers and implementers need to understand the structure of the web of policies they might influence or be influenced by. Also, following Scottish Government commitments to democratic inclusion, this can make engaging with policy more difficult if the connections between legislation, consultations and the final instruments being implemented on individual farms are not obvious to non-farming stakeholders or new entrants to farming.

³ VCS – Voluntary Coupled Support; LFASS – Less Favoured Area Support Scheme; AECS – Agri-Environment Climate Scheme; RPID – Rural Payments and Inspectorate Division; FAS – Farm Advisory Service; SEPA – Scottish Environment Protection Agency; IACS – Integrated Assessment and Control Survey; PfG – Programme for Government.

Additionally, understanding and explicitly defining such interconnections could help in monitoring and appraising the efficacy of implementation in meeting the goals of higher-level legislation.

4.2.3 Coherence Relationships

We also conducted an analysis of the connectivity between the 11 selected agricultural policies and other policies in the full sample in R, including policy instruments that were relevant. The overall sample and number of links is smaller than in Figure 3, as we took links made from our 11 selected agricultural policies as a starting point. As illustrated below, the R analysis revealed 78 links between a total of 42 policy documents. Again, this suggests good awareness of the need for policies to connect with one another.

This analysis revealed links between our 11 selected agricultural policies (framed with bold borders) and other policies in all four domains. Most of the links are gold, as one might expect as the starting point was links from these 11 policies. There are links to or from all five climate policies in our sample, but only to 10 of the possible 22 environment policy documents; and 7 of 17 socio-economic policy documents. Furthermore, there are no references in the climate change policy documents to the agricultural policies; and only five references made by socio-economic policies to the agricultural policies. We noted that two of the 22 AFF policies (Crofting Plan, 2019; and the proposed Land Reform Bill, 2024) do not have any document references made from our selected 11 started policies. This might suggest that there is a well understood need for agricultural policies to work with climate, environment and socio-economic policies to advance a coordinated and transformative policy agenda, but that there are still some areas where links could be strengthened.

With our restricted starting point, Figure 6 shows only two reciprocal relationships between the agriculture policies and others in our sample, and both of these were between policies in the agricultural domain (between Agriculture Act 2020; and the Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill 2023; and between the Agricultural Routemap 2023 and the Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill, 2023). The same caveats around the age of policies apply as were discussed in section 4.1.2 but one might expect to see more cross-referencing particularly within the slew of documents relating to the changes in the policy area between 2020-2024. This reiterates earlier findings that there is limited cross-referencing among the policies. Combined with the finding that most of the links are from the AFF policies to the other domains and not vice-versa, it seems important to ensure that the receiving policies recognise the connections for the coherence to work in practice.

Figure 6: Links between selected agricultural policies. The diagram includes policy instruments, shown as diamond shapes, otherwise the colouring and shapes repeat from Figure 1. See Annex 3 for abbreviations.

Where we examined the types of references from the subset of agricultural policies to others in the sample, it became clear that connections are often made between Acts and the steering strategies and instruments that sit beneath other Acts. For example, the new Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill 2023 makes references to 17 policies. However, these references back to older climate, environment and socio-economic policies only include four primary legislation documents: two climate, one environment (Good Food Nation (Scotland) 2022) and one socio-economic document (Crofting Reform 2009). The remaining connections are mediated through agricultural steering strategies and instruments, rather than linking directly between the Acts.

4.2.3.1 Diagonal Coherence

We refer to the relationships that connect the objectives of one policy (as set out in primary legislation) to the instruments in another policy document, particularly where the policy is in a different policy domain, as ‘diagonal’ coherence. Policy coherence is therefore not limited to neat horizontal or vertical connections but includes diagonal relationships between different domains and types of policies. When dealing with a cross-cutting topic such as land use transformation, we contend that understanding such diagonal forms of coherence is essential.

The instruments shown in Figure 6 include Cross Compliance, GAECs and the wider SRDP, which were revealed to be important instruments for delivering a variety of agricultural, forestry or fishery policies, as well as for environmental and socio-economic policies. Examples of diagonal relationships included where regulation (cross-compliance) and funding (AECS, SRDP) within the current agricultural policies are essential to delivery of the objectives set out in other policies such as:

- Socio-economic: Crofting Reform Act (2019) (reference from Act to instrument)
- Environment: Soil Framework, National Peatland Plan, Deer Management Plan (reference from strategies to instruments)

However, in most cases shown in Figure 6, the link was from the agricultural policy instruments to the other domains such as:

- AECS references Biodiversity Strategy (2023) and River Basin Management Plan (RBMP) (2021)
- SRDP references Climate Change Act (2019); Biodiversity Strategy (2023); RBMP (2021), Flood Risk Management (FRM) Act (2009), Economic Transformation Strategy (2022)

When we reviewed the full sample (n=66, not n=42 shown Figure 6) then we also found that these instruments were important to a suite of policies concerned with non-agricultural objectives, as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5: How selected agricultural policy instruments are referenced by other policy documents

Policy	AFF	Climate	Environment	Socio-Economic
SRDP 2021 (9 references to this instrument)	LRRS 2017 Woodland expansion 2009 Agriculture bill 2023 Cross compliance 2014 Woodland removal 2009 Ag routemap 2023		Nat peatland plan 2015 Soil framework 2009 Deer Mgmt 2020	Biomass action plan 2007
Cross-Compliance 2014 (4 references to this instrument)	LUS 2021 Ag routemap 2023 Crofting plan 2021		Water Env regs 2011	
GAEC 2022 (7 references to this instrument)	SRDP 2021 LUS 2021 LRRS 2017		Soil framework 2009	Biomass action plan 2007

Policy	AFF	Climate	Environment	Socio-Economic
	Woodland expansion 2009 Ag routemap 2023			
AECS 2022 (3 references to this instrument)	Ag routemap 2023 Agriculture bill 2023		Nat peatland plan 2015	
LFASS 2022 (2 references to this instrument)	Ag routemap 2023 Agriculture bill 2023			
Woodland removal 2009	SRDP 2021			

These diagonal coherence relationships were all stated in the documentation but often needed to be derived from careful reading of the documents, rather than having the relationships explicitly explained. For example, AECS as part of the SRDP is implicitly expected to act as an instrument that meets a wide range of policy objectives, but from analysis of policy documentation on AECS, it is not explicitly clear to which policies this instrument is supposed to relate. These implied interactions mean the policy documents in this subset can lack clearly stated roles, responsibilities and expectations for how these interactions would be operationalised and sustained. This makes it difficult for policies to cohere with one another, or for other policy domains to cohere with the agricultural policies, yet these practices are going to be necessary to achieve the objectives of the new agricultural reform programme. Some degree of diagonal coherence is intentionally designed into the current agricultural support programme through cross compliance as a requirement of the farm support payments, but our analysis, shown in Figure 6 and Table 5 suggest that these connections were not always shown in explicit references to the underlying policy documents.

The agricultural policy instruments also interact horizontally with other regulatory environmental instruments such as Controlled Activities Regulations 2011/21; Environmental Impact Assessment regulations (1999); and Conservation (Natural Habitats etc.) Regulations 1994. There is also a direct relationship from the Town and Country planning regulations to cross-compliance in Figure 6; and from cross-compliance to the Water Environment regulations. These horizontal connections between instruments, without stated references to the relevant primary legislation were an unexpected finding.

4.3 Coherence within Government

Here the broad screening data and in-depth analysis data were analysed to see patterns associated with ‘owners’ and ‘enforcers’. Owners are the parts of government responsible for designing policy and setting both the objectives and designing the instruments to deliver those objectives. Enforcers, in this analysis, are the wider governmental actors that encourage the uptake of voluntary instruments, promote the actions in the steering strategies and ensure compliance with the statutory/regulatory instruments. The findings consider both aspects.

4.3.1 Policy Owners

We defined ‘owners’ as the entity that is currently responsible for each policy. This was not always clear on the policy documents, as the body responsible may be different to the one that wrote it, or that was initially responsible for it. We therefore looked beyond the policy documents, for indications in the Scottish Government webpages. There were a relatively wide range of different parts of government involved as owners of our policy documents. Regarding the details of different owner organisations, there are 19 different owner organisations either owning or co-owning our sample of policies (see Annex 5: Table of policy owners). Most of the owner organisations are Scottish Government Directorates (n=13 Directorates), but there is also SEPA, NatureScot, Forestry Commission Scotland, and an Advisory Group on Economic Recovery. In addition, the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union jointly own one of the policies in our sample. There are three main entities that are responsible for most of the policies. These are the Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate (n=29 policies), the Environment and Forestry Directorate (n=26 policies), and the Energy and Climate Change Directorate (n=17 policies) (see Figure 7). Next is the Marine Scotland Directorate (n=6 policies). The remaining bodies all own 3 policies or fewer.

We also considered the connectivity between owners of each policy in our analysis in R, as shown in Figure 7. The figure suggests that directorates do link to policies beyond their immediate policy domain. For example, not all policies relating to productive land use originate from the agricultural directorate. For example, some of the land reform and forestry policies are owned or co-owned by the Environment and Forestry Directorate, whilst other land reform and forestry policies are owned by Agriculture and Rural Development Directorate. However, there may be results that are an artefact of our coding, for example, some of the environmental policies associated with ‘other’ are owned by environmental government agencies (e.g. SEPA, NatureScot) and likewise, some of the ‘socio-economic’ policies relate to energy if not climate change, and therefore are very aligned with the Energy and Climate Change Directorate.

Out of our 66 policies sampled, 43 of them are owned by a single body. In this way, Figure 7 also provides another lens on the analysis. For example, looking at references in Figure 3 and Figure 6, steering strategies like the Land Use Strategy (LUS, 2021) and the Biodiversity Strategy (2023) have multiple connections but here single, different, directorates appear to be responsible for their design and implementation.

The remaining 23 policies are co-owned by two or more bodies. Figure 7 also shows that there is a small number of policies that are highly connected by being owned by two or more bodies (in centre of the figure). There appear to be more shared policies between Agriculture and Rural Development and Environment and Forestry directorates than between the other policy owners. These policies tend to be quite recent, (an outlier is the Wild Animals and Natural Environment Act (2011)), but there are other recent policy documents that are not co-owned. These many-to-many relationships suggest a strong foundation for policy coherence, if these links are actively working collaborations and there is better signposting within policy documents. However, the findings of Sections 4.1 and 4.2

emphasise the importance of active collaboration and explicit signposting of connections, such that different owners have clear expectations regarding how policies should interact.

Figure 7: Scottish Government Directorates responsible for the policies in our sample. Here only primary legislation and strategies are shown. The hexagons represent three named directorates and 'Other' representing 17 other directorates and national agencies. The policy abbreviations can be found in Annex 3.

4.3.2 Policy enforcers

We also considered the enforcers of each policy. We understood 'enforcers' as actors that encourage the uptake of voluntary instruments, promote the actions in the steering strategies and ensure compliance with the statutory/regulatory instruments. As with the policy owners, we often had to infer ownership from what was written in the documents but it was not always clear; and there may be cases with multiple enforcers what we have

missed. We concentrated on government directorates and organisations within the policy realm. We stopped short of looking at influences on policy by NGOs and lobby groups or views on policy implementation by land managers, or by other land-based businesses.

Overall, 22 different enforcers were specifically mentioned as responsible for the implementation and/or monitoring and policing of policies. These included a mixture of Scottish Government directorates, as well as agencies such as SEPA and NatureScot. In some cases the enforcers were more diffuse, being attributed to local authorities, Scottish ministers in general, and other public and conservation bodies, as compared to the analysis of owners, in which specific directorates were mentioned. There were also 14 policies in which the enforcer was either not mentioned, unclear, or seemed to lack a specific enforcer. In some cases, this could be explained or justified by the fact the policies were statements or visions that only included recommendations rather than mandates (e.g. *Towards a Robust, Resilient Wellbeing Economy for Scotland: Report of the Advisory Group on Economic Recovery (2020)*). Whilst there will be organisations responsible, using the principle of what is available in the documents or on the hosting website, meant these organisations were not visible to us.

We found that sector-specific enforcers tend to just have a single, relevant policy. For example, the District Salmon Fishery Boards and Scottish Canals were only found to be enforcing the River Basin Management Plan for Scotland (2021-2027). Similarly, the Fair Work, Employability and Skills Directorate was only associated with the enforcement of the *Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021)*. Meanwhile, more generalised actors (e.g. NatureScot, Land Commission, Local Authorities, Rural Services and Payments/RPID, Scottish Ministers, Scottish Government (General)) are responsible for enforcing a wider spread of policies. Conversely, a total of eight policies were shown to have multiple enforcers, such as *The Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009*, the River Basin Management Plan for Scotland (2021-2027), and *Climate Change Act (2009)*. This reflects the same patterns as shown in Figure 7, that instruments in the agricultural domain are implemented by a range of policy actors across different institutions. It also highlights new insights on vertical coherence regarding how central government policy makers direct work by their agencies; and illustrates that there are gaps that may impede vertical or diagonal coherence working well in practice.

5 Summary answers to our research questions:

The approach is interpretative policy analysis, which focuses on meaning-making processes within policy documents; and how these meanings are communicated and understood by those reading and using the documents. This is an inductive approach to build up a holistic and systemic understanding of how policies interact and cross-reference. This section addresses all the original research questions, although our initial aim was only to try to answer the first two questions. Therefore, the later sections 5.3 to 5.5 are more tentative and will require further analysis to develop these answers.

5.1 Are there synergies, gaps or conflicts in the way current land use policies are supporting land use transformations?

Our broad coherence screening suggests that there is limited attention being given to issues of climate change adaptation and justice issues in our sample of land-based policy documents. These gaps are potentially being addressed by the proposed revision to the Adaptation Strategy and the launch of the Land Use and Agriculture Just Transition Plan. These potential gaps were also reflected in the further analyses in R, with less references between socio-economic policies and the other policy domains, and a different pattern of connections between adaptation and climate mitigation policies. In general, we did not see many references to non-environmental policies that can have a strong bearing on land use and agriculture (e.g. planning, energy, tourism). Given that many farms are diversifying beyond food production into on-farm agri-tourism, housing, food processing or energy production, it seems important that these other policy domains are considered, and any coherence expectations (in either direction) are identified. The visualisations (see Figure 3 and Figure 6) also highlighted few connections to the land reform policies (including in the more recent policy documents).

The analysis of the published documents suggests that all the policies are believed to be synergistic (i.e. they were all seen to advance land use transformation goals), and there are no substantive conflicts being signalled that will impede horizontal coherence or mean the need for explicit trade-offs at the level of the policy objectives. However, the limited evidence of reciprocal coherence relationships may signal that there are undeclared conflicts or trade-offs; or at least, limits to synergies. There was insufficient material within the documents reviewed to date to assess definitively if there would be conflicts between instruments or in the implementation practices. The nature of the research method (taking claims in printed documents at face value) meant that the lack of explicit references to conflicts or trade-offs between policy objectives was not surprising.

However, prior research suggests that increasing the ambition and reach of beyond the food production and farmer income agricultural policy objectives is both contested and resisted. Previous research on policy instruments in the same domain [16] suggests that policies are designed to be coherent at the level of objectives and instruments, with any difficulties arising at the level of implementation. However, given the difficulty of 'doing it all' with limited resources and potential resistance from the land-based sector to radical land use change [17], this assertion deserves more attention. There are two aspects to this – firstly to have explicit recognition that conflicts may arise within policy design; and therefore to start

to quantify trade-offs in space and time. With an increase in ambition for transformation, identifying conflicts and trade-offs may need to become part of the process of framing objectives and agreeing appropriate measures. Articulating these aspects in policy design statements may increase their legitimacy through an open and honest presentation of the need for change, and the full range of costs and benefits plus the burden sharing involved in such transformations.

The second part concerns policy implementation. Our analysis suggests that whilst these policies are presenting a progressive narrative of change and transformation, it is not always clear how connections between policies work in practice and exactly what these coherence relationships are supposed to deliver in terms of the policy's desired outcomes. The many connections highlighted in our analysis imply awareness of other policies, but this does not necessarily mean all policies are aligned to those they reference. Without understanding these details, it is unclear if the narratives of change can be translated into delivery. It is quite possible that without clear pathways from coherence intentions to delivery of coherent policy instruments, there could be a lag in realising land-use transformations. In other words, the need to respond to the triple crises of climate, biodiversity and cost of living is broadly accepted, but the specific pathways to achieving these outcomes are less clear.

5.2 Are there problems of vertical, diagonal and/or horizontal coherence within existing land use policies?

Overall, the situation is complex. We found connections across the different policy domains considered, and an encouraging density of relationships between policies. However, there were few reciprocal relationships between policies, especially across domains, and particularly between environmental policies and socio-economic policies.

There were also gaps in the coherence analysis regarding how our sample related to non-agricultural policies. There were links between our 11 selected policies and others across all domains, but again, limited reciprocal relationships. Beyond the above summary regarding gaps and lack of attention to conflict; we also found that diagonal coherence, that is, using the instruments of cross-compliance and agricultural payments to deliver multiple non-agricultural policy objectives, was very important but not very visible in the policy documentation. There were also questions of how (beyond regulation) to incorporate land managers that are not receiving agricultural payments, arising from the diagonal coherence relationships whereby delivery of wildlife, water and climate objectives from other primary legislation relies on such land (see section 4.2.3.1). We are unsure how diagonal coherence can work where there is a mix of land being managed by both those who do and do not claim agricultural payments (non-SAF businesses). This matters if policy objectives are delivered through emergent landscape scale outcomes. The measures may require coordinated if not collective action by land managers but raise questions of blocking and free riding.

Our findings suggest that whilst coherence and transformation is sought, at least in the policy discourse, there is a lack of clarity regarding who will ensure coherence happens. Some policy arrangements, such as policy bodies being responsible for policies beyond their area of focus, and some policies being the responsibility of multiple bodies, could contribute towards coherence. However, the lack of clarity in who is responsible for each policy, as well as the frequent lack of explicit indications as to how different policies fit in with each other, make it difficult for the non-expert to navigate the policy landscape; and could raise questions of accountability, a common governance challenge. In addition, there are no indications as to how policy directorates work to make their policies coherent. Nor are there many visible mechanisms and resources to make the coherence function at the implementation stage, including the roles of advisors, inspectors, and the land managers themselves. Furthermore, the policy documents were not easy to navigate for the non-expert and the position statements that set the transformative narrative for the agricultural reform routemap do not use consistent terminology. This is important as without building a common understanding of the processes and components of coherence, it is unlikely that coherence will be delivered.

Despite these pitfalls, our analysis does show that there has been an increase over time in the efforts made towards coherence. For example, the more recent version of the National Planning Framework 4 has more explicit references to other policies than the previous version of this policy had (National Planning Framework 3).

5.3 How could policy coherence support land use transformations?

The *a priori* assumption is that greater coherence is desirable and at an abstract level this is clearly true if only as less coherent policy would be obviously undesirable. There are arguments that coherence promotes more specifically desirable outcomes such as efficiency and effectiveness.

Taking efficiency, the material in the sister JHI C3-1 ongoing Storytelling consultation analysis [18] reflects, and wider literature [19] suggests, that there is a desire for a more coherent approach to land use policies. The desire to reduce ‘red tape’ and ‘compliance costs’ [20] can be seen as part of the conservative response to the crises facing European farming. There is a great deal of change occurring within the agriculture, rural development and environment policy landscape(s) at the present, whilst the landowners, managers and users are also simultaneously responding to other pressures created by inflation, compliance with net zero and biodiversity targets, creating a sense of increasing pressures on the land-based businesses. Therefore, recognising the multiple benefits already being delivered by diagonal coherence, and explicit steps to avoid duplication and to pull policies together for a more streamlined and tractable delivery might help soften resistance to change.

At the same time, the latest state of the nature reporting [21] and climate change risk assessment [22] results highlight the need for increased ambition and effectiveness of delivery. Therefore, it is important that the agricultural reforms are seen to be responding to these wider societal changes, and there are clear mechanisms to capture and demonstrate the contribution. For example, how the coherence of agricultural and

environmental policies can help achieve substantive improvements in the metrics being measured, e.g. through the Natural Capital Asset Index within the National Performance Framework.

Yet even if it were possible to demonstrate that greater coherence makes individual policies more effective and more efficient and enhances overall outcomes then that still leaves key mechanistic questions of how changes in policy coherence are achieved and the attribution of cause and effect. From the available data, it will be difficult to add much more detail to answer this research question. However, further reflection could sharpen up the message and help target responses to the research penultimate question below.

5.4 What are the opportunities to improve or sustain coherence?

There is evidence that ambition for coherence and transformation is increasing over time. There are areas of strong coherence on paper, which could be further developed through ensuring there are shared practices and reciprocal processes to really drive coherence from the level of objectives to co-designed measures and strong implementation/enforcement. Naming diagonal coherence is the first step in making it more visible, and actively taking it into account in policy design. Our assumption is that diagonal coherence has been well understood in government for many years, however, there can be value in making the implicit explicit and developing clear and transparent practices regarding how these relationships will work in the future.

Whilst we may be experiencing a moment of resistance to change, the fact that so many land-related policies are being revised or refreshed at present offers a rare opportunity to actively promote policy coherence. This could be as simple as taking care to use precise references to each other's policies, with supporting hyperlinks to connect to the texts; plain English explanations of how nested policies are designed to fit together; and a clear statement of different government roles and responsibilities. Figure 7 above illustrates areas where there are opportunities to build on shared responsibilities and where further relationships between policy owners and enforcers could be developed.

From wider literatures on farmer behaviour, addressing the least addressed goals of Climate Change Adaptation and Just Transitions (especially the distribution of costs and benefits) might also be resonant with land manager community. Dealing with constraints on land-based businesses (both productive and diversified such as tourism or energy production) created by extreme weather events (floods, droughts, wildfires) are more immediately relevant to their daily livelihoods than the global processes of reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions. The references to the Climate Change Adaptation Strategy in Figure 3 highlights that it is an important site for coherence. The asymmetrical relationships between the more than 50,000 Scottish holdings and the main wholesalers and retailers also underpin wider farming protests. It is possible that addressing the justice and adaptation goals more explicitly as part of policy coherence may help with winning hearts and minds required to embed the narrative of transformation into reality.

There are also questions on roles, responsibilities and decision-making processes within government, and between government and stakeholders. There may be opportunities to do

more with the land managing and land using communities. There are further questions about the role that paid advisors or facilitators can play to help foster and maintain coordinated landscape action, such as for example, on habitat or aquatic restoration. Are such advisers considering coherence relationships, do they have the resources needed to advise on them, and are the advisers being actively considered as a key part of policy implementation? Finally, there is little to no reference to the role of private finance or blended finance in the policy documents, yet these emerging market/private policies may have considerable influence on how coherence is being or will be practiced by land managers. It is a topic that we will be unlikely to be able to explore in the current research within the Land Use Transformations project but it is a topic being considered within other parts of the research programme, such as Natural Capital (JHI-D5-1).

5.5 How can coherence be monitored more effectively in the future?

Recognising need for coherence is a good start but to be effectively used the concept it is important to start to monitor it. However, this requires building on individual policy monitoring and evaluation processes and our analysis to date shows that there were very few explicit targets or indicators associated with many of the policy documents screened in the goals spreadsheet, making evaluation of their progress problematic. The National Performance Framework provides a common vision and some indicators of progress; and other policies, such as those associated with the water environment or climate mitigation have clear targets, but these targets or indicators are not necessarily visible in the documentation of the full range of policies with which they are expected to cohere. The explicit inheritance of expectations and targets from primary objectives to instruments and implementation and a feedback reality check of feasibility back up the hierarchy would make horizontal, vertical and diagonal coherence visible to those reviewing, deliberating on and adapting policies.

We found, however, very little visible evidence of how these coherence relationships are monitored to see what works, or references to improving the capacity and knowledge base of those implementing or auditing compliance with the policy so that these coherence relationships are developed and effective. Whilst there were monitoring frameworks available and comprehensive agricultural data through the Agricultural Census and IACS, it was not clear how these were providing a feedback loop to see if the overall objectives were being delivered, as there are no explicit targets for agricultural policy at present. The proposed agricultural policy framework has some targets, at least from analysis of the consultation documents, such as GHG emission reduction by 24% by 2025; Proposed Natural Environment statutory targets; real living wages paid to rural workers; 18,000 ha per annum tree planting and 250,000 ha peatland restored. These are targets that are set as part of other policies, again highlighting the diagonal and horizontal coherence is an expectation within the policy framework. These targets will need a pathway to achieving them, including just burden sharing, fair attribution of progress and clear lines of responsibility and accountability. They will also need to be monitored. The detailed data already available for the land use sector could be well deployed to connect land use management practices with these wider targets and objectives, so that we can link management with outcomes and adapt policies if required.

6 Policy Implications

The above findings, derived from our analysis of policy coherence suggest the following policy implications:

Holistic approach

The policy coherence findings highlight there are already important connections for land use transformation between all four policy domains (agriculture, fishery and forestry; climate; environment; socio-economic). This reinforces the fact that Scottish land use is a broad topic with cross-governmental implications.

Horizontal coherence

The analysis shows that there are many connections between policies and across domains, but few are reciprocal. This raises the issues of: a) why not all relationships are reciprocal; and b) whether there are any mechanisms by which those responsible for policies referred to by other policies are made aware of and able to respond to these connections.

Vertical coherence

The analysis shows that relationships within nested agricultural policies are not always clearly or explicitly explained in policy documentation. It would be useful for policy documents to explain the relationships clearly and explicitly between agricultural policies, especially to help non-agricultural experts.

Diagonal coherence

Objectives associated with one policy may be met through the instruments of another policy, including crossing policy domains (e.g. environmental policy objectives by agricultural policy instruments). Not only is this not always explicit or clearly explained, but it is also unclear if these references are resourced, and the owners and enforcers are aware of their responsibilities.

Governance

Many policy documents connect to multiple directorates, which creates a strong foundation for coherence. This raises the question of what mechanisms exist for making these connections on paper, work well in practice? The lack of clarity as to who 'owns' or is responsible for each policy may be intentional to reduce policy 'silos'. However, this makes difficult to recognise roles and responsibilities. This obscures accountability and the practical aspects of who to involve in policy coherence processes.

7 Next Steps

Within the Governance activity of the Land Use Transformations project, further work will focus on the last three research questions considering potential solutions and ways of working that could help promote policy coherence delivery.

Within this, we have potential next steps to work through, presented in order:

- Further exploration of our data, particularly thinking about

- the other actors beyond government involved (agencies implementing and inspecting compliance with policy instruments; land managers themselves);
- the funds and budgets associated with the different policies;
- the existing targets, indicators and monitoring processes for each policy, that could help also monitor policy coherence.
 - Whilst the institutions and policies associated with private market organisations are also important for coherence, this is likely to remain beyond our scope for the next year. However, aspects of ‘equivalence’ from industry certified standards might be included in the monitoring and evaluation analysis.
- We would like to consider how the policy coherence themes connect with the Land Use Story Telling data on the narratives present in the SG consultations and those coming from non-governmental actors, another part of the Land Use Transformations project. There are useful overlaps between the two strands of analysis. We would like to bring together the data from Scottish Government documents with the views expressed by consultees on these policies.
- Bringing together these observations with other strands of the Land Use Transformation projects which pay attention to whether the goals of the different policies are being met (or not) in the final round of Quantitative Story Telling (the policy-led analysis within the Land Use Transformations project).

We will also submit the analysis to wider peer review in a journal paper, by further developing the analyses of where coherence is working or needs attention. This will include extending our literature review on what works for policy coherence, although initial reviews have not returned many empirical examples of coherence in action to date.

We welcome feedback from on policy priorities, for example, we would be willing to support the RESAS analysts working on how to monitor and evaluate the Agricultural Reform Programme from a social research perspective.

Annex 1: List of Policy Documents used in Horizontal Screening

Agriculture, Forestry and Land Use (23)

Agriculture Reform Route Map (2023)
 Agriculture (Retained EU Law and Data) (Scotland) Act 2020
 Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill (2023)
 Agri-Environment Climate Scheme (2022)
 Crofting Reform (Scotland) Act 2010
 Crofting: national development plan 2021
 Delivering our Vision for Scottish Agriculture: Proposals for a new Agriculture Bill (2022)
 Forestry and Land Management (Scotland) Act (2018)
 Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs) 2022
 Just Transition: Land Use and Agriculture (2023)
 Land Reform Act (2003)
 Land Reform Act (2016)
 Land Use Strategy (2021)
 Less Favoured area Support Scheme (2022)
 Local Food strategy consultation (2021)
 Proposed new Land Reform Bill (during 2023)
 Scotland's Forestry Strategy 2019–2029
 Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement (2017)
 Scottish Rural Development Programme (2021-2024)
 Sustainable and regenerative farming - next steps: statement (2022)
 The Common Agricultural Policy (Cross-Compliance) (Scotland) Regulations 2014
 The Scottish Government's Policy on Control of Woodland Removal (2009)
 The Scottish Government's Rationale For Woodland Expansion (2009)

Climate Change (5)

Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019
 Climate Change Act (2009)
 Climate Ready Scotland: Second Scottish Climate Change Adaptation Programme 2019-2024
 Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021)
 Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032

Environment (21)

Conservation (Natural Habitats, &c.) Regulations 1994 (as amended in Scotland) (Habitats Regulations)
 Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009
 Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2022)
 National Parks (Scotland) Act 2000
 Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act 2004
 NatureScot's Scotland's National Peatland Plan (2015)
 Nitrates Directive: The Action Programme for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (Scotland) Regulations 2008
 Peatland and energy: Draft policy statement (2016)

River Basin Management Plan (2021-2027)
 Scotland's Biodiversity strategy: a consultation (June 2022)
 Scottish Biodiversity Strategy to 2045 (December 2022)
 Scottish biodiversity strategy to 2045 - Tackling the nature emergency (2023)
 Scottish Soil Framework (2009)
 Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 2009/128/EC
 The Conservation of Salmon (Scotland) Regulations 2016
 The Environment Strategy for Scotland: vision and outcomes (2020)
 The management of wild deer in Scotland: Deer Working Group report (2020)
 The Scottish Plant Health Strategy (2016)
 The Water Environment (Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Regulations 2011
 The Water Environment (Miscellaneous) (Scotland) Regulations 2017
 Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act 2011

Socio-Economic (17)

A Scotland for the future: opportunities and challenges of Scotland's changing population (2021)
 Bioenergy Update (2021)
 Biomass Action Plan (2007)
 Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act (2022)
 Housing to 2040 (2021)
 National Performance Framework (2022)
 National Planning Framework 3 (2014)
 National Planning Framework 4 (consultative draft) 2022
 Scotland's Energy Strategy Position Statement (2021)
 Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation (2022)
 Scottish Energy Strategy: The future of energy in Scotland (2017)
 Scottish Planning Policy 2014
 The National Plan for Scotland's Islands (2019)
 The Town and Country Planning (Environmental Impact Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations 2017
 Tourism in Scotland: the economic contribution of the sector (2018)
 Towards a Robust, Resilient Wellbeing Economy for Scotland (2020)
 Working Together to Build A Greener, Fairer, Independent Scotland (AKA The Bute House Agreement) (2021)

Annex 2: List of Goals used for horizontal coherence screening

1. Goal 1 (Climate Mitigation) is defined as "The policy contributes to the Scottish Government Net Zero goal of 100% reduction on 1990/1995 baseline GHG emissions by 2045, which is intended to limit global temperature rise."
2. Goal 2 (Biodiversity) is defined as "The policy contributes to the Scottish Government's commitment that by 2045 we will have substantially restored and regenerated biodiversity across our land, freshwater and seas, by ensuring species and habitats are diverse and healthy."
3. Goal 3 (Climate Adaptation) is defined as "the policy takes account of climate adaptation pressures, so the implementation measures and actions remain feasible as climatic conditions and ecological responses change."
4. Goal 4 is defined as "The policy contributes to the maintaining or increasing the economic prosperity of land-based rural industries."
5. Goal 5 is defined as "the policy contributes to ensuring there is procedural and distributional justice considerations for those managing and using rural land."

The definition of Land Use Transformations in the Hutton C3 project Glossary is "the degree of change is substantial, system wide, beyond incremental and is initiated rather than reacted to (contrasting with system collapse)."

Annex 3: Policy Abbreviations

In order of Figure 3, with instruments added in alphabetical order at the end of each domain.

Policy	Policy abbreviation
Scotland's Forestry Strategy 2019–2029	Forestry strategy 2019
Just Transition Land Use and Agriculture (2023)	Just transition (LU) 2023
Land Use Strategy (2021)	LUS 2021
Delivering our Vision for Scottish Agriculture: Proposals for a new Agriculture Bill (2022)	Agriculture vision 2022
Agricultural Reform Route Map (2023)	Ag routemap 2023
Crofting: national development plan (2021)	Crofting plan 2021
Sustainable and regenerative farming - next steps: statement (2022)	Farming statement 2022
Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement (2017)	LRRS 2017
Local Food strategy (2021)	Local food strategy 2021
The Scottish Government's Rationale for Woodland Expansion (2009)	Woodland expansion 2009
Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill (2023)	Agriculture bill 2023
Forestry and Land Management (Scotland) Act (2018)	Forestry 2018
Land Reform Act (2016)	LRSA 2016
Agriculture (Retained EU Law and Data) (Scotland) Act 2020 -analysed through the help of the policy memorandum	Agriculture 2020
Land Reform Act (2003)	LRSA 2003
Proposed new Land Reform Bill (during 2023)	Land reform bill 2024
Agri-Environment Climate Scheme (2022)	AECS 2022
The Common Agricultural Policy (Cross-Compliance) (Scotland) Regulations (2014)	Cross compliance 2014
Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs) (2022)	GAECS 2022
Less Favoured area Support Scheme (2022)	LFASS 2022
Scottish Rural Development Programme (2021-2024)	SRDP 2021
The Scottish Government's Policy on Control of Woodland Removal (2009)	Woodland removal 2009
Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032	CCP update 2018
Climate Ready Scotland: Second Scottish Climate Change Adaptation Programme 2019-2024	CCAP 2019
Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021)	Just transition 2021
Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act (2019)	Climate change 2019
Climate Change Act (2009)	Climate change 2009
Scottish biodiversity strategy to 2045 - Tackling the nature emergency (2023)	Biodiversity Strategy 2023
The Environment Strategy for Scotland: vision and outcomes (2020)	Environment strategy 2020
River Basin Management Plan for Scotland (2021-2027)	RBMP 2021

NatureScot's Scotland's National Peatland Plan (2015)	Nat peatland plan 2015
Scottish Biodiversity Strategy post-2020: A statement of intent. (December 2020)	Bio S: statement 2020
Biodiversity strategy: consultation (2022)	Bio S: consultation 2022
The Scottish Plant Health Strategy (2016)	Plant health 2016
Scottish Soil Framework (2009)	Soil framework 2009
The management of wild deer in Scotland: Deer Working Group report (2020)	Deer Mgmt 2020
Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act (2022)	GF nation 2022
Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act (2004)	Nature conservation 2004
Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act (2009)	FRM act 2009
Peatland and energy: Draft policy statement (2016)	Peatland & energy 2016
Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act (2011)	WANE act 2011
Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 2009/128/EC	Pesticides directive 2009
Nitrates Directive: The Action Programme for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (Scotland) Regulations (2008)	Nitrates directive 2008
National Parks (Scotland) Act (2000)	National parks 2000
Conservation (Natural Habitats, &c.) Regulations 1994 (as amended in Scotland) (Habitats Regulations)	Conservation regs 1994
Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2022)	Nat cap investment 2022
The Conservation of Salmon (Scotland) Regulations (2016)	Salmon regulations 2016
The Water Environment (Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Regulations (2011)	Water env regs 2011
The Water Environment (Miscellaneous) (Scotland) Regulations (2017)	Water env regs 2017
National Planning Framework 4 (2021)	NPF4 2021
The National Plan for Scotland's Islands (2019)	Islands plan 2019
Scottish Government and Scottish Green Party Shared Policy Programme WORKING TOGETHER TO BUILD A GREENER, FAIRER, INDEPENDENT SCOTLAND (AKA The Bute House Agreement) (2021)	Bute house 2021
Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation (2022)	Econ trans strategy 2022
Housing to 2040 (2021)	Housing 2021
National Planning Framework 3 (2014)	NPF3 2014
A Scotland for the future: opportunities and challenges of Scotland's changing population (2021)	Population strategy 2021
National Performance Framework (2022)	Nat perform fwk 2022
Scottish Energy Strategy: The future of energy in Scotland (2017)	Energy strategy 2017
Bioenergy Update (2021)	Bioenergy update 2021
Biomass Action Plan (2007)	Biomass action plan 2007
Scotland's Energy Strategy Position Statement (2021)	Energy strategy 2021

Towards a Robust, Resilient Wellbeing Economy for Scotland: Report of the Advisory Group on Economic Recovery (2020)	Wellbeing economy 2020
Scottish Planning Policy (2014)	Planning policy 2014
Tourism in Scotland: the economic contribution of the sector (2018)	Tourism 2018
Crofting Reform (Scotland) Act 2010	Crofting reform 2010
The Town and Country Planning (Environmental Impact Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations (2017) Schedule 1 + schedule 2	T & C planning 2017

Annex 4: Table of policy relationships

Abbreviation	Policy mechanism group	Policy domain group	Links	Links in	Links out	Links to AFF Land Use	Links to Socio-Economic Land Use	Links to Environment	Links to Climate Change	Links to Primary legislation	Links to Steering strategies	Links to Instruments
Just transition (LU) 2023	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	14	1	13	5	2	2	4	2	11	0
LUS 2021	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	14	10	4	2	1	1	0	0	2	2
Forestry strategy 2019	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	13	12	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Ag routemap 2023	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	10	2	8	6	0	1	1	2	3	3
Agriculture vision 2022	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	10	3	7	1	2	1	3	2	5	0
Crofting plan 2021	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	6		6	2	1	2	1	2	4	0
LRRS 2017	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	5	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
Farming statement 2022	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	5	2	3	2	0	1	0	2	1	0
Local food strategy 2021	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	3	1	2	1	0	1	0	2	0	0
Woodland expansion 2009	Steering strategies	AFF Land Use	3		3	3	0	0	0	0	1	2

Agriculture bill 2023	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	21	4	17	11	0	3	3	6	7	4
Forestry 2018	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	5	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	0
LRSA 2016	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	5	4	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Agriculture 2020	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	4	3	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
LRSA 2003	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	4	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Land reform bill 2024	Primary legislation	AFF Land Use	3	1	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0
SRDP 2021	Instruments	AFF Land Use	15	9	6	1	1	3	1	2	3	1
Cross compliance 2014	Instruments	AFF Land Use	7	4	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	3
GA ECS 2022	Instruments	AFF Land Use	7	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AECS 2022	Instruments	AFF Land Use	5	3	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	0
LFASS 2022	Instruments	AFF Land Use	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Woodland removal 2009	Instruments	AFF Land Use	1	-	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
CCP update 2018	Steering strategies	Climate Change	17	13	4	2	1	0	1	2	2	0
CCAP 2019	Steering strategies	Climate Change	15	7	8	3	2	3	0	2	6	0
Just transition 2021	Steering strategies	Climate Change	4	3	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Climate change 2019	Primary legislation	Climate Change	9	8	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Climate change 2009	Primary legislation	Climate Change	7	6	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Biodiversity Strategy 2023	Steering strategies	Environment	24	15	9	2	2	3	2	1	7	1

Environment strategy 2020	Steering strategies	Environment	18	10	8	0	3	3	2	0	8	0
RBMP 2021	Steering strategies	Environment	9	4	5	1	0	3	1	0	5	0
Nat peatland plan 2015	Steering strategies	Environment	8	3	5	3	1	0	1	1	2	2
Bio S: consultation 2022	Steering strategies	Environment	5		5	3	0	2	0	0	5	0
Bio S: statement 2020	Steering strategies	Environment	5	2	3	0	1	1	1	0	3	0
Soil framework 2009	Steering strategies	Environment	5	2	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
Plant health 2016	Steering strategies	Environment	3		3	1	0	1	1	0	3	0
Deer Mgmt 2020	Steering strategies	Environment	1		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Nature conservation 2004	Primary legislation	Environment	6	5	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
FRM act 2009	Primary legislation	Environment	4	2	2	0	0	2	0	1	0	1
GF nation 2022	Primary legislation	Environment	4	4								
Peatland & energy 2016	Primary legislation	Environment	2		2	0	1	1	0	0	2	0
WANE act 2011	Primary legislation	Environment	2	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
National parks 2000	Primary legislation	Environment	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nitrates directive 2008	Primary legislation	Environment	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pesticides directive 2009	Primary legislation	Environment	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Water env regs 2011	Instruments	Environment	5	2	3	1	0	2	0	2	0	1
Conservation regs 1994	Instruments	Environment	4	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Nat cap investment 2022	Instruments	Environment	2	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Water env regs 2017	Instruments	Environment	2	-	2	0	0	2	0	1	0	1
Salmon regulations 2016	Instruments	Environment	1	-	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
NPF4 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	19	10	9	3	4	2	0	0	9	0
Econ trans strategy 2022	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	16	8	8	0	4	2	2	0	8	0
Islands plan 2019	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	12	2	10	1	4	2	3	1	9	0
Bute house 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	10	1	9	2	5	1	1	3	6	0
Energy strategy 2017	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	7	4	3	0	2	0	1	0	3	0
Housing 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	7	7								
NPF3 2014	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	7	4	3	1	1	1	0	0	3	0
Population strategy 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	6	2	4	1	3	0	0	1	3	0

Nat perform fwk 2022	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	5	5								
Biomass action plan 2007	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	4	-	4	3	0	1	0	0	2	2
Bioenergy update 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	2	-	2	0	1	0	1	0	2	0
Energy strategy 2021	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	1	-	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Wellbeing economy 2020	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	1	-	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Tourism 2018	Steering strategies	Socio-Economic Land Use	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Planning policy 2014	Primary legislation	Socio-Economic Land Use	3	-	3	1	1	0	1	1	2	0
Crofting reform 2010	Primary legislation	Socio-Economic Land Use	1	-	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
T & C planning 2017	Instruments	Socio-Economic Land Use	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Annex 5: Table of policy owners

	Owner (or co-owner)	Policy
European bodies	Council of the European Union, and the European Parliament (jointly)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 2009/128/EC
Non-departmental Scottish public bodies/ Advisory groups	NatureScot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NatureScot's Scotland's National Peatland Plan (2015)
	SEPA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> River Basin Management Plan for Scotland (2021-2027)
	SG Advisory Group on Economic Recovery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Towards a Robust, Resilient Wellbeing Economy for Scotland: Report of the Advisory Group on Economic Recovery (2020)
	Forestry Commission Scotland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Scottish Government's Policy on Control of Woodland Removal (2009) THE SCOTTISH GOVERNMENT'S RATIONALE FOR WOODLAND EXPANSION (2009)
Scottish Government Directorates	Chief Economist Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scotland's National Strategy for Economic Transformation (2022)
	Constitution Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scottish Government and Scottish Green Party Shared Policy Programme WORKING TOGETHER TO BUILD A GREENER, FAIRER, INDEPENDENT SCOTLAND (AKA The Bute House Agreement)
	Culture and Major Events Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourism in Scotland: the economic contribution of the sector (2018)
	External Affairs Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Scotland for the future: opportunities and challenges of Scotland's changing population (2021) (strategy/plan)
	Performance, Delivery and Resilience Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Performance Framework
	Population Health Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Food Strategy
	International Trade and Investment Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2022) Local Food strategy
	Economic Development Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crofting: national development plan Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032 Housing to 2040
	Local Government and Housing Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Planning Framework 3 (2014) Scottish Planning Policy 2014 National Planning Framework 4
	Marine Scotland Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scottish Biodiversity Strategy post-2020: A statement of intent Biodiversity strategy: consultation Conservation (Natural Habitats, &c.) Regulations 1994 (as amended in Scotland) (Habitats Regulations) The Conservation of Salmon (Scotland) Regulations 2016 The Environment Strategy for Scotland: vision and outcomes (2020) Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act (2022)
	Energy and Climate Change Directorate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity strategy: consultation Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009 Climate Ready Scotland: Second Scottish Climate Change Adaptation Programme 2019-2024 Crofting: national development plan The Environment Strategy for Scotland: vision and outcomes (2020) Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032 Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) (Scotland) Act 2019

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021) • Bioenergy Update • Biomass Action Plan (2007) • Housing to 2040 • Peatland and energy: Draft policy statement (2016) • Scotland’s Energy Strategy Position Statement • Scotland’s Energy Strategy: The future of energy in Scotland (2017) • Climate Change Act (2009) • The Water Environment (Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Regulations 2011 • Just Transition Land Use and Agriculture (2023)
<p>Environment and Forestry Directorate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scottish Biodiversity Strategy post-2020: A statement of intent. • Biodiversity strategy: consultation • Conservation (Natural Habitats, &c.) Regulations 1994 (as amended in Scotland) (Habitats Regulations) • Flood Risk Management (Scotland) Act 2009 • Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act 2004 • The Water Environment (Miscellaneous) (Scotland) Regulations 2017 • Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act 2011 • Crofting: national development plan • Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2022) • National Parks (Scotland) Act 2000 • Sustainable and regenerative farming - next steps: statement (2022) • The Environment Strategy for Scotland: vision and outcomes (2020) • Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032 • Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021) • Bioenergy Update • The Town and Country Planning (Environmental Impact Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations 2017 Schedule 1 + 2 • Forestry and Land Management (Scotland) Act (2018) • Land Reform Act (2003) • Scotland's Forestry Strategy 2019–2029 • Scottish Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement (2017) • Scottish Soil Framework (2009) • The management of wild deer in Scotland: Deer Working Group report (2020) • The Scottish Plant Health Strategy • The Water Environment (Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Regulations 2011 • Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill (2023) • Scottish biodiversity strategy to 2045 - Tackling the nature emergency (2023)
<p>Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scottish Biodiversity Strategy post-2020: A statement of intent. • Biodiversity strategy: consultation • Nature Conservation (Scotland) Act 2004 • Nitrates Directive: The Action Programme for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (Scotland) Regulations 2008 • Wildlife and Natural Environment (Scotland) Act 2011 • Agri-Environment Climate Scheme • Crofting Reform (Scotland) Act 2010 • Crofting: national development plan

- Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs) 2022
 - Interim Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital (2022)
 - Scottish Rural Development Programme (2021-2024)
 - Sustainable and regenerative farming - next steps: statement (2022)
 - The National Plan for Scotland's Islands (2019)
 - Update to the Climate Change Plan 2018-2032
 - Just Transition - A Fairer, Greener Scotland: Scottish Government response (2021)
 - The Common Agricultural Policy (Cross-Compliance) (Scotland) Regulations 2014
 - Delivering our Vision for Scottish Agriculture: Proposals for a new Agriculture Bill
 - Bioenergy Update
 - Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act (2022)
 - Less Favoured area Support Scheme
 - Local Food strategy
 - Proposed new Land Reform Bill (during 2023)
 - The Scottish Plant Health Strategy
 - Land Use Strategy (2021)
 - Agriculture (Retained EU Law and Data) (Scotland) Act 2020
 - Land Reform Act (2016)
 - Agricultural Reform Route Map (2023)
 - Just Transition Land Use and Agriculture (2023)
 - Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill (2023)
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